

Stem cells and growth factors in patients with intermittent claudication: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials.

Search strategies

Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) in the Cochrane Library

Date Run: 05/04/2021 16:26:01

ID	Search	Hits
#1	stem cell transplantation	8726
#2	(bone marrow cell*):ti,ab,kw	7930
#3	(mesenchymal stem cell* or mesenchymal stromal cell*):ti,ab,kw	1733
#4	(stem cell*):ti,ab,kw	13103
#5	(cell transplant*):ti,ab,kw	13183
#6	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 #5	15804
#7	MeSH descriptor: [Intermittent Claudication] explode all trees	950
#8	(intermittent claudic*):ti,ab,kw	1968
#9	(vascular claudication):ti,ab,kw	911
#10	(claudic*):ti,ab,kw	2641
#11	#7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10	2641
#12	MeSH descriptor: [Peripheral Vascular Diseases] explode all trees	3279
#13	MeSH descriptor: [Peripheral Arterial Disease] explode all trees	1093
#14	(peripheral vascular disease*):ti,ab,kw	4823
#15	(peripheral arterial disease*):ti,ab,kw	4512
#16	#12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15	8752
#17	#11 OR #16	10289
#18	MeSH descriptor: [Angiogenic Proteins] explode all trees	1401
#19	MeSH descriptor: [Fibroblast Growth Factors] explode all trees	406

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#20	MeSH descriptor: [Endothelial Growth Factors] explode all trees	193
#21	MeSH descriptor: [Angiogenesis Inducing Agents] explode all trees	49
#22	MeSH descriptor: [Erythropoietin] explode all trees	2148
#23	MeSH descriptor: [Platelet-Derived Growth Factor] explode all trees	148
#24	MeSH descriptor: [Hepatocyte Growth Factor] explode all trees	67
#25	MeSH descriptor: [Vascular Endothelial Growth Factors] explode all trees	1285
#26	(Del-1):ti,ab,kw OR (VEGF):ti,ab,kw OR (FGF):ti,ab,kw OR (HGF):ti,ab,kw OR (PDGF):ti,ab,kw	5911
#27	(PDGF):ti,ab,kw OR (EPO):ti,ab,kw OR (GM-CSF):ti,ab,kw OR (GMCSF):ti,ab,kw OR (growth factor):ti,ab,kw	22546
#28	(angiogen*):ti,ab,kw OR (angiopoietin*):ti,ab,kw OR (erythropoietin*):ti,ab,kw	9205
#29	#18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR #24 OR #25 OR #26 OR #27 OR #28	258432
#30	#6 OR #29	269875
#31	#17 AND #30	2183

Embase Ovid

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ID	Search	Hits
1	exp stem cell transplantation/	161043
2	stem cell*.ti,ab.	415658
3	bone marrow cell*.ti,ab.	30311

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4	(mesenchymal stem cell* or mesenchymal stromal cell*).ti,ab.	76828
5	cell transplant*.ti,ab.	119482
6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	501674
7	exp intermittent claudication/	9845
8	intermittent claudic*.ti,ab.	6412
9	vascular claudication.ti,ab.	94
10	claudic*.ti,ab.	15194
11	7 or 8 or 9 or 10	18808
12	exp peripheral vascular disease/	1883349
13	peripheral vascular disease*.ti,ab.	14792
14	peripheral arterial disease*.ti,ab.	14513
15	exp angiogenic protein/	905
16	exp fibroblast growth factor/	20030
17	exp endothelial cell growth factor/	2204
18	exp angiogenic factor/	10659
19	exp erythropoietin/	36384
20	exp platelet derived growth factor/	25031
21	exp scatter factor/	17973
22	exp vasculotropin/	114703
23	Del-1.ti,ab.	487
24	VEGF.ti,ab.	103390
25	FGF.ti,ab.	24577
26	HGF.ti,ab.	15307
27	PDGF.ti,ab.	21882
28	PD-GF.ti,ab.	6
29	EPO.ti,ab.	16846
30	GM-CSF.ti,ab.	27446
31	GMCSF.ti,ab.	1792
32	growth factor.ti,ab.	410210
33	angiogen*.ti,ab.	167395
34	angiopoietin.ti,ab.	8233

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35	erythropoietin.ti,ab.	33971
36	15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35	681519
37	6 or 36	1131044
38	exp crossover-procedure/ or exp double-blind procedure/ or exp randomized controlled trial/ or single-blind procedure/	731320
39	(((((random* or factorial* or crossover* or cross over* or cross-over* or placebo* or double*) adj blind*) or single*) adj blind*) or assign* or allocat* or volunteer*).af.	920052
40	38 or 39	1438319
41	(exp animal/ or exp invertebrate/ or nonhuman/ or animal experiment/ or animal tissue/ or animal model/ or exp plant/ or exp fungus/) not (exp human/ or human tissue/)	7122531
42	40 not 41	1309427
43	exp peripheral occlusive artery disease/	175044
44	12 or 13 or 14 or 43	1886957
45	11 or 44	1888682
46	37 and 42 and 45	2869

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ID	Search	Hits
1	randomized controlled trial.pt.	525461
2	controlled clinical trial.pt.	94087
3	randomized.ab.	439378
4	placebo.ab.	194776
5	drug therapy.fs.	2293490
6	randomly.ab.	297652

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7	trial.ab.	462593
8	groups.ab.	1836735
9	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8	4499925
10	exp animals/ not humans.sh.	4804835
11	9 not 10	3852947
12	exp Stem Cell Transplantation/	85521
13	stem cell*.ti,ab.	232876
14	bone marrow cell*.ti,ab.	22435
15	(mesenchymal stem cell* or mesenchymal stromal cell*).ti,ab.	41575
16	Cell Transplant*.ti,ab.	55540
17	12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	281572
18	exp Intermittent Claudication/	8052
19	intermittent claudic*.ti,ab.	4727
20	vascular claudication.ti,ab.	48
21	claudic*.ti,ab.	9963
22	18 or 19 or 20 or 21	13051
23	exp Peripheral Vascular Diseases/	54348
24	peripheral vascular disease*.ti,ab.	9178
25	peripheral arterial disease*.ti,ab.	8306
26	exp Angiogenic Proteins/	61888
27	exp Fibroblast Growth Factors/	31743
28	exp Endothelial Growth Factors/	8081
29	exp Angiogenesis Inducing Agents/	6629
30	exp Erythropoietin/	23775
31	exp Platelet-Derived Growth Factor/	13660
32	exp Hepatocyte Growth Factor/	7938
33	exp Vascular Endothelial Growth Factors/	56164
34	Del-1.ti,ab.	401
35	VEGF.ti,ab.	58151
36	FGF.ti,ab.	16791
37	HGF.ti,ab.	9534

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38	PDGF.ti,ab.	15075
39	PD-GF.ti,ab.	1
40	EPO.ti,ab.	10826
41	GM-CSF.ti,ab.	17967
42	GMCSF.ti,ab.	445
43	growth factor.ti,ab.	295438
44	angiogen*.ti,ab.	102152
45	angiopoietin*.ti,ab.	5187
46	erythropoietin*.ti,ab.	24380
47	26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46	444737
48	17 or 47	697313
49	exp Peripheral Arterial Disease/	8542
50	23 or 24 or 25 or 49	64303
51	22 or 50	73776
52	11 and 48 and 51	450

ClinicalTrials.gov	03/05/2021	stem cell OR growth factor Interventional Studies Peripheral Arterial Disease
World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform	03/05/2021	Peripheral arterial disease AND stem cell Peripheral arterial disease AND growth factor
ISRCTN Register	03/05/2021	Peripheral arterial disease AND stem cell Peripheral arterial disease AND growth factor

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